

Numerical Investigation of Waves Interacting with Rigid and Flexible Plates

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Abstract

Coastal structures, such as oil and gas rigs, offshore wind turbine platforms, breakwaters, flood protection systems and wave energy converters, need to be appropriately designed to withstand wave loading. These structures experience stresses under wave loading and may significantly deform. A mutual interaction is triggered between the waves and structure, which may have significant effects and result in structural failures in extreme cases. Experimental and numerical investigations of wave-structure interaction (WSI) phenomena have been increasingly conducted in the last decade. However, an accurate understanding of WSI effects is still challenging. The present study focuses on the numerical modelling of waves impacting rigid and flexible plates with the toolbox solids4foam. The numerical model was validated with available laboratory experiments for a solitary wave impacting a flexible plate. A total of 117 tests with a range of linear and solitary waves impacting plates located offshore and onshore with different stiffnesses and inclinations have been conducted. In the onshore tests, the time series of the force on the plates confirm the previously observed double peak. The first peak was due to the initial impact of the surge, while the second peak was related to the collapse of the water column following the wave run-up. New semi-empirical correlations are proposed based on the offshore wave energy to predict the overland flow energy and force on the plate. These findings improve our understanding of WSI and may support the design of coastal structures.

Keywords: Flexible structures; Foam-extend; Long waves; Numerical modelling; Wave-structure interaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

The impact of waves on coastal structures poses a serious challenge for a range of coastal applications such as oil and gas rigs, offshore wind turbine platforms, breakwaters, flood protection systems and wave energy converters. These structures may undergo significant deformations due to wave loading and the fluid flow may in turn be affected by the structural displacements. The physics governing these phenomena, referred to as wave-structure interaction (WSI), leads to a mutual interplay between the waves and structure potentially resulting in structural failure.

In the last decade, researchers showed a growing interest in the investigation of WSI phenomena in coastal applications. Some of the most relevant benchmark studies include the dam break with an elastic gate (Antoci et al., 2007), wave impacts on offshore walls (Kimmoun et al., 2009; Linton et al., 2013; Didier et al., 2014) and the dam break wave impacting a flexible obstacle (Liao et al., 2015). Linton et al. (2013) conducted large-scale experiments in a 104 m long, 3.66 m wide and 4.57 m deep wave flume to investigate the performance of wood walls impacted by tsunamis. The most flexible wall resulted in smaller forces compared to stiffer walls. The measured forces were found to agree well with the following equation (Cross, 1967)

$$F_I = \frac{1}{2} \rho_w g h_s^2 + C_f \rho_w h_s \bar{u}_s^2, \quad [1]$$

where F_I expresses the force on a vertical boundary due to a surge where ρ_w is the water (subscript w) density, h_s the water depth, $\bar{u}_s$ the depth-averaged velocity and C_f is a coefficient related to the inclination of the free water surface.

Due to the maturity of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and computational structural dynamics (CSD), numerical modelling shows a great potential to investigate WSI. Mesh-based methods (He and Kashiwagi, 2012; Chen et al., 2014; Sotiropoulos and Yang, 2014; Liao et al., 2015; Hu et al., 2016; Tukovic et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2020), e.g. the Finite Volume Method (FVM) and Immersed Boundary Method (IBM), and mesh-free methods (Antoci et al., 2007; Didier et al., 2014; Heller et al., 2016; Khayyer et al., 2018; 2019), e.g. Smoothed

Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH), have been successfully applied to model WSI phenomena. Mesh-based methods are generally more computationally efficient, while mesh-free methods handle moving interfaces and large deformations more effectively. In some studies, mesh-based and mesh-free methods have been coupled to complement their advantages (Kumar et al., 2015; Rao et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2019).

Unfortunately, an accurate understanding of WSI effects is still a major challenge. The present study focuses on the numerical investigation of waves impacting rigid and flexible plates with the open-source toolbox `solids4foam` implemented in `foam-extend 4.0`. The main aims are to (i) validate the numerical model `solids4foam` with an experiment of Kimmoun et al. (2009), (ii) provide new physical insights into linear and solitary waves impacting offshore plates of different stiffnesses and inclinations, (iii) provide new physical insights into solitary waves impacting onshore plates of different stiffnesses and to (iv) investigate the transformation of a solitary wave into overland flow. The numerical model and set-ups are addressed in Section 2. The validation of `solids4foam` along with representative results of the offshore and onshore tests are included in Section 3, followed by the Conclusions and Outlook in Section 4.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Governing Equations

The toolbox `solids4foam` handles fluid-solid interaction phenomena by separately solving the fluid and solid governing equations. The fluid is modelled as incompressible and Newtonian, for which the following equations apply

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad [2]$$

$$\frac{\rho}{\partial t} \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \rho(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} = -\nabla p + \rho \nabla \cdot (\mu \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}' \mathbf{u}') + \rho \mathbf{g} \quad [3]$$

where $\mathbf{u}$ is the fluid velocity vector, t the time, p the pressure, ρ the fluid density, μ the fluid dynamic viscosity, $\mathbf{u}' \mathbf{u}'$ the turbulent stress tensor and $\mathbf{g}$ the gravitational acceleration vector. The $k - \varepsilon$ turbulence model (Launder and Spalding, 1974) was selected in the present study. For water-air flows, the Volume of Fluid (VOF) method (Hirt and Nichols, 1981) is applied. This is based on the fraction volume $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$, with $\alpha = 0$ denoting air (subscript a), $\alpha = 1$ water and the fluid properties are computed as

$$\rho = \rho_w \alpha + \rho_a (1 - \alpha) \quad [4]$$

$$\mu = \mu_w \alpha + \mu_a (1 - \alpha) \quad [5]$$

The parameter α is updated over t through the following transport equation

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} \alpha) + \nabla \cdot [\alpha(1 - \alpha) \mathbf{u}_r] = 0 \quad [6]$$

For the solid domain, assuming a nonlinear geometry model, the following equation was solved

$$\rho_s \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{d}_s}{\partial t^2} + \nabla \cdot [(J \mathbf{D}_F^{-T}) \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s] = \rho_s \mathbf{g} \quad [7]$$

where $\mathbf{d}_s$ is the solid (subscript s) displacement vector, ρ_s the solid density, $\mathbf{D}_F = I + (\nabla \mathbf{d}_s)^T$ the deformation gradient, with the identity matrix I , J the Jacobian determinant of $\mathbf{D}_F$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s$ the stress tensor.

The fluid-solid coupling was performed based on a partitioned approach (Cardiff et al., 2018). For each time step, the fluid domain is updated by solving Eqs. [2], [3] and [6]. Thereafter the fluid loadings at the fluid-solid interface are estimated and applied to the solid domain. Consequently, the solid domain is solved (Eq. 7) and the new solid velocities are used to update the fluid mesh.

2.2 Numerical Set-up and Test Programme

Waves impacting plates of different stiffnesses, located either offshore or onshore, were investigated based on 117 tests. Figure 1(a) shows the numerical set-up for the offshore tests. The plate, of height $l = 30$ m and thickness $s = 2$ m, was clamped on a 35 m high substructure located 4 times the wavelength L from the upwave boundary. Simulations involved a range of linear and solitary waves impacting plates of Young's moduli $E = 1, 30$ and 1000 GPa and inclinations $60^\circ \leq \beta \leq 90^\circ$ (Table 1). These mimic extreme scenarios of real applications, with $E = 1$ GPa representing a range of plastics. A resolution of $\Delta x = \Delta z = 0.15$ m was used in a $25 \text{ m} \times 32 \text{ m}$ refined area in front of the plate and $\Delta x = \Delta z = 0.60$ m in the remainder of the domain.

Figure 1. Numerical set-ups with the most relevant parameters: (a) offshore and (b) onshore plate.

Table 1. Test programme.

Wave type	Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Offshore	Onshore
	Water depth	h	m	42.5, 50.0, 57.5	2, 3, 4
	Plate height	l	m	30	3
	Plate inclination	β	$^\circ$	60, 75, 90	90
	Young's modulus	E	GPa	1, 30, 1000	1, 1000
	Plate thickness	s	m	2	0.15, 0.30
	Dimensionless rigidity	$Es^3/(12\rho_wgh^4)$	-	0.006 to 20.830	0.112 to 1.433×10^4
	Plate density	ρ_s	kg/m ³	1500, 8000	1500, 8000
	Plate support condition	-	-	Top free	Top free, roller support
	Shore freeboard	z_f	m	-	0, 1, 2
	Shore length	l_s	m	-	4
	Shore inclination	β_s	$^\circ$	-	30
Linear waves	Wave height	H	m	2.62 to 3.55	-
	Relative wave height	H/h	-	0.046 to 0.080	-
	Wave period	T	s	6, 8, 10	-
	Relative wave period	$T(g/h)^{0.5}$	-	2.48 to 3.84	-
Solitary waves	Wave amplitude	a	m	3.56 to 3.75	0.9, 1.2, 1.5
	Relative wave amplitude	a/h	-	0.06 to 0.09	0.225 to 0.750

The plate was positioned on the horizontal section of the shore for the 45 onshore tests (Figure 1b). Solitary waves with wave amplitudes $0.9 \text{ m} \leq a \leq 1.5 \text{ m}$ and water depths of $h = 2, 3$ and 4 m were investigated. For each impacting wave, 5 plates with different E , s and support conditions were used (Table 2). In the "top free" case the plate was supported at the foundation and the top was free to move. In the "roller support" the plate was supported at the foundation and the horizontal displacements d_x at the top end were prevented. Resolutions of $\Delta x = \Delta z = 2.50$ cm and $\Delta x = \Delta z = 1.25$ cm in a $140 \text{ cm} \times 300 \text{ cm}$ refined area were used.

The simulations were run on the High Performance Computing cluster Augusta at the University of Nottingham using 40 Central Processing Units (CPUs) and 100 GB of memory. In the offshore layout, the solitary wave tests took up to approximately 10 h to simulate 30 to 33 s and the linear wave tests took up to 34 h for a simulation time of 110 s. The onshore tests required up to 20 h to simulate 6 to 10 s.

Table 2. Classification of the 5 onshore plates for each impacting wave.

Notation	E (GPa)	ρ_s (kg/m ³)	s (m)	Support
R	1000	8000	0.30	Top free
RS1	1	1500	0.30	Roller support
RS2	1	1500	0.15	Roller support
TF1	1	1500	0.30	Top free
TF2	1	1500	0.15	Top free

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Validation of the Numerical Model

The validation of the numerical model for rigid plates can be found in Attili et al. (2021). The numerical model for flexible plates is validated herein with an experiment from Kimmoun et al. (2009). The experimental set-up consisted of a wave flume with a sloped shore and a 1.0 m high plastic plate located 14.5 m from the wave maker (Figure 2a). The test involved a solitary wave with $a/h = 0.12$ impacting the plate with $s = 5.00$ mm, $E = 3.25$ GPa and $\rho_s = 1190$ kg/m³. The plate was clamped at the foundation and simply supported at $z = 0.872$ m.

The wave travelled along the shore and broke as a plunging breaker before impacting the plate. Figure 2(b) shows the laboratory and numerical snapshots of the wave-plate interaction at $t = 0.03$ s, where $t = 0.00$ s is the instant when the wave front reaches the plate. The water surface elevation is reproduced well in this simulation; however, the size of the entrapped air pocket is underestimated. Figure 2(c) shows the horizontal plate displacements d_x over t observed in the laboratory experiment and in the present study at $z = 0.35$ m. The simulation overestimates d_x with a deviation of 33% at the maximum peak. The numerical model captures the complex physics of the phenomenon and overall provides similar results as the laboratory observations.

Figure 2. Validation of the numerical model with an experiment of Kimmoun et al. (2009): (a) experimental set-up, (b) comparison between the experimental and numerical snapshots at $t = 0.03$ s and (c) horizontal displacement of the plate d_x at $z = 0.35$ m.

3.2 Offshore tests

Figure 3 shows a snapshot series of a solitary wave impacting an offshore flexible plate with $a/h = 0.088$, $s = 2.00$ m and $E = 1$ GPa. In the present study, $t = 0.00$ s is defined as the instant when the wave front reaches the plate. The wave travelled along the flume and impacted the plate before being reflected. The dimensionless force $F/(\rho_w gh^2)$ and displacement d_x/l of the top end of the plate are shown over the relative time

$t(g/h)^{0.5}$ in Figure 4(a) and (b) for the flexible and rigid plates with $E = 1$ and 1000 GPa, respectively. The force F is due to the hydrostatic and wave pressures combined, acting on the upwave side of the plate. The flexible plate deforms under the wave loading reaching a maximum d_x of approximately 0.54 m. In this test, T is theoretically ∞ and significantly larger than the natural period of the plate $T_s \approx 3.4$ s. This results in a quasi-static loading acting on the plate, which does not oscillate over the investigated time range (Figure 4b).

Figure 3. Snapshot series of a solitary wave impacting an offshore plate with $a/h = 0.088$, $s = 2.00$ m and $E = 1$ GPa showing the velocity $u = (u_x^2 + u_y^2)^{0.5}$, pressure contours (MPa) and the horizontal displacement d_x .

Figure 4. Offshore test: time series of the relative (a) force $F/(\rho_w g h^2)$ and (b) dimensionless horizontal displacement d_x/l at the top end of the plate with $E = 1$ and 1000 GPa for a solitary wave with $a/h = 0.088$.

Figure 5(a) and (b) shows $F/(\rho_w g h^2)$ and d_x/l for a linear wave with $a/h = 0.047$ and $T(g/h)^{0.5} = 2.88$ for $E = 1$ and 1000 GPa. $F/(\rho_w g h^2)$ for the rigid and flexible plates show once again negligible differences. In this test, the ratio T/T_s is significantly smaller than the previously discussed case and the plate oscillates with a period close to the wave period $T = 6$ s.

Figure 5. Offshore test: time series of the relative (a) force $F/(\rho_w g h^2)$ and (b) horizontal displacement d_x/l at the top end of the plate with $E = 1$ and 1000 GPa for a linear wave with $a/h = 0.047$ and $T(g/h)^{0.5} = 2.88$.

3.3 Onshore tests

In the onshore tests, the wave runs-up the shore and impacts the plate, as shown in the snapshot series in Figure 6 for a solitary wave with $a/h = 0.60$ and plate TF2. When the wave runs-up the plate a water column is observed in front of the plate. This collapses after its kinetic energy is transformed into potential energy.

Figure 6. Snapshot series of a solitary wave impacting an onshore plate with $a/h = 0.60$, $s = 0.15$ m and $E = 1$ GPa showing the velocity $u = (u_x^2 + u_y^2)^{0.5}$, pressure contours (kPa) and the horizontal displacement d_x .

Figure 7. Onshore test with $a/h = 0.6$: (a) time series of the relative force $F/(\rho_w g h^2)$ and (b) dimensionless horizontal displacement d_x/l along z/h when F is maximum for 5 plates with different properties (Table 2).

Figure 7(a) shows the time series of $F/(\rho_w g h^2)$ for the 5 plates in Table 2 due to a solitary wave with $a/h = 0.6$. A first peak F_I is observed after the initial impact, followed by a second peak F_{II} due to the collapse of the water column, confirming the laboratory observations of Linton et al. (2013). These two peaks were observed in all the onshore tests of Table 1, apart from the tests with $a/h = 0.225$, where only a single peak was observed. This is most likely due to the relatively small a and large L . $F_{II} \geq F_I$ in most of the tests, up to 3.3 times. As shown in Figure 7(a), the stiffness of the plate has a negligible effect on F in these tests.

Figure 7(b) shows the dimensionless horizontal displacements d_x/l along z/h for the same 5 plates at the instant when F_{II} was observed. The plate R shows a negligible d_x and the maximum d_x are observed for the most deformable plates, namely RS2, TF1 and TF2. As expected, the plates RS2 showed a maximum d_x near the centre, and TF1 and TF2 at the top end.

3.3.1 Transformation into overland flow

Once the wave runs-up the shore, it transforms into overland flow before impacting the plate (Figure 8). Based on the depth h_s and the depth-averaged velocity $\bar{u}_s$ of the overland flow, the force F_I can be predicted with Eq. [1]. In the present study, h_s and $\bar{u}_s$ are defined in the middle of the horizontal section of the shore (2 m from the plate). Figure 9(a) shows the comparison between the predicted (subscript *pred*) with Eq. [1] and numerical (subscript *num*) $F_I/(\rho_w g h^2)$. $F_{I,pred}/(\rho_w g h^2)$ was computed assuming $C_f = 1$, with the numerical h_s and $\bar{u}_s$ resulting in the maximum values of $F_{I,pred}$. Only the simulations with the plate R have been included in the following analyses. As shown in Figure 9(a), $F_{I,pred}/(\rho_w g h^2)$ agrees with $F_{I,num}/(\rho_w g h^2)$ well. However, the prediction of h_s and $\bar{u}_s$ remains challenging.

Figure 8. Sketch with the main parameters of a solitary wave and its transformation into overland flow.

During wave propagation over the shore, the wave energy is partially transformed into potential and kinetic energies of the overland flow. The remainder of E_w is consumed by various mechanisms, namely bottom friction, reflection from the shore and wave breaking. According to Li and Raichlen (2003), the solitary wave energy per unit width E_w is

$$E_w = \frac{8}{3\sqrt{3}} \rho_w g (ah)^{3/2} \quad [8]$$

The energy per unit area of the overland flow E_{of} due to the kinetic and potential components can be written as

$$E_{of} = \frac{1}{2} \rho_w h_s \bar{u}_s^2 + \rho_w g h_s (h + z_f + h_s/2) \quad [9]$$

Assuming that $E_w \propto E_{of}$, the following equation was derived (Figure 9b)

$$\frac{E_{of}}{[\rho_w g (h + z_f + a)^2]} = \frac{5}{2} \frac{E_w}{[\rho_w g (h + z_f + a)^3]} - 0.06 \quad [10]$$

The intercept 0.06 in Eq. [10] takes the energy consumed by bottom friction, reflection from the shore and wave breaking into account.

Figure 9. Overland flow: (a) comparison of the predicted (Cross, 1967) and numerical $F_I/(\rho_w g h^2)$ ($R^2 = 0.93$) and (b) the dimensionless energy of the overland flow $E_{of}/[\rho_w g (h + z_f + a)^2]$ versus the dimensionless wave energy $E_w/[\rho_w g (h + z_f + a)^3]$ with Eq. [10] ($R^2 = 0.98$) for the rigid plates (R in Table 2).

The first peak of the force F_I was also expressed as a function of E_w as (Figure 10)

$$\frac{F_I}{[\rho_w g (h + z_f + a)^2]} = \frac{5}{4} \frac{E_w}{[\rho_w g (h + z_f + a)^3]} - 0.04 \quad [11]$$

Figure 10. The dimensionless force $F_I/[\rho_w g (h + z_f + a)^2]$ versus the dimensionless wave energy $E_w/[\rho_w g (h + z_f + a)^3]$ with Eq. [11] ($R^2 = 0.91$) for the rigid plates (R in Table 2).

Eqs. [10] and [11] provide overall a good prediction of E_{of} and F_I and most of the data are within the ± 25 and $\pm 30\%$ boundaries (Figures 9b and 10), with the exception of the test with $a/h = 0.75$ for Eq. [11]. In this test surging breaking was observed in proximity of the shore, resulting in a violent impact on the plate with $F_I \geq F_{II}$. This may explain the observed deviations.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

Linear and solitary waves impacting plates located offshore and onshore have been investigated based on the numerical model solids4foam. The wave-structure interaction (WSI) effects, e.g. force and plate response, have been addressed for a range of wave conditions and plate stiffnesses. Young's moduli $1 \text{ GPa} \leq E \leq 1000 \text{ GPa}$ have been used to simulate extreme scenarios for real applications, with $E = 1 \text{ GPa}$ representing a range of plastics. The main conclusions of the present study are:

- The numerical model solids4foam has been validated with a laboratory solitary wave impacting a flexible plate from Kimmoun et al. (2009);
- 117 numerical experiments of linear and solitary waves impacting offshore plates of inclinations $\beta = 60, 75$ and 90° and $E = 1, 30$ and 1000 GPa have been conducted;
- A total of 45 tests of solitary waves impacting onshore plates of different stiffnesses have also been performed;
- The energy of the overland flow E_{of} and the first peak of the force F_l have been correlated with the offshore wave energy E_w (Eqs. 10 and 11).

Ongoing and future work focuses on 3D numerical tests of waves impacting flexible offshore plates and own laboratory experiments for further validation of the numerical model.

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